

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP3 - Development of the Virtual Ecosystem for
Research Activation (VERA)

EU-Citizen.Science connector

date 30.01.2023

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COESO has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014-2020)
SwafS-27-2020 - Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation, under Grant Agreement No.101006325

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Deliverable 3.7

EU-Citizen.Science connector

Grant Agreement number	: 101006325
Project acronym	: COESO
Project title	: Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues
Funding Scheme	: H2020-EU.5. - SCIENCE WITH AND FOR SOCIETY
Topic	: SwafS-27-2020 - Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation
Project's coordinator Organization	: EHESS-OpenEdition
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Website	: https://coeso.hypotheses.org
WP and tasks contributing	: WP3, Task 3.6 Interoperability development with EU-Citizen.science platform
WP leader	: Net7
Task leader	: Ibercivis
Dissemination level	: PU
Due date	: 31/01/2023
Delivery date	: 30/01/2023
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I. Executive summary

The aim of this document is to complement the release of the actual COESO project Deliverable 3.7 - EU-Citizen.Science connector, due in M25 (31st January 2023).

This deliverable describes the context for the connection between the VERA and the EU-Citizen.Science platforms. Sharing VERA projects using EU-Citizen.Science Application Programming interface (API) will make it possible, on the one hand, to give visibility to the projects developed within VERA and, on the other, to be part of a growing ecosystem of citizen science (CS) information sharing.

In order to do that, the EU-Citizen.Science project provides an API that allows, among other tasks, to register, login, push and pull projects automatically from other platforms. This API was built on top of the EU-Citizen.Science models using the Django REST framework.

During the *Task 3.6 Interoperability development with EU-Citizen.science platform*, Net7 and Ibercivis teams have been working to build all the technical infrastructure - mainly on the VERA side - to make this connection possible. In order to do that, API documentation has been generated - part of this documentation is shown in this deliverable. A development server replica of the EU-Citizen.Science platform has been deployed in order to test the connection between both platforms.

Furthermore, the EU-Citizen.Science platform has a moderation process that guarantees the quality of the CS projects stored in it. ECSA (legally responsible for the EU-Citizen.Science platform) team has collaborated during the duration of this task to explain how this moderation process is executed and set out the mechanisms by which VERA projects will be accepted into EU-Citizen.Science.

I. Structure of the document

This document is structured in VII main sections, describing:

- Section I: Executive summary
- Section II: The EU-Citizen.Science platform and its general structure and the PPSR Core
- Section III: Why make this connection? The EU-Citizen.Science ecosystem
- Section IV: Connection components, API description and its usage
- Section V: VERA built-in connection to EU-Citizen.Science
- Section VI: Formal acceptance of VERA's projects within the EU-Citizen.Science platform
- Section VII: Conclusions

II. The EU-Citizen.Science platform, its general structure & the PPSR Core

EU-Citizen.Science is a closed project financed in the H2020 framework program under grant agreement No. 824580. It started in January 2019 and finished in December 2021. The ambition of the EU-Citizen.Science project ('the Project') was to build on the growing impact of citizens participating in research across the full range of scientific enquiry, by developing a sustainable platform to act as a mutual learning space for citizen science (CS), focusing on Europe but relevant globally. EU-Citizen.Science's aim was to engage equally with CS participants, practitioners, researchers, policy makers and society as a whole throughout the course of the project. One of the main ways of achieving this was the development of the EU-Citizen.Science platform.

The overall vision for the EU-Citizen.Science platform ('the Platform') was to aid the mainstreaming of CS in Europe, such that it becomes an appreciated and widely established means for the democratisation of science in Europe.

The building of the Platform was being pursued through three interconnected lines of activity:

- Coordinating CS actions, and making use of existing resources in the presently fragmented CS landscape in Europe;
- Engaging quadruple helix stakeholders at local, national and European levels;
- Creating a mutual learning space and a set of comprehensive, co-designed training modules for different target audiences.

The vision for the Platform was to become a co-created central hub for knowledge sharing, coordination, and action at the European level. The platform includes:

- Projects that are engaging the public in research via citizen science activities
- Resources that are useful for citizen science practitioners
- Training resources and materials on citizen science as a practice
- Training modules on citizen science in a wide range of themes
- Other platforms (world-wide, national, regional and local level)
- Organisations that are involved in citizen science projects and research
- Events calendar
- A blog
- Forum for questions, conversations, and collaboration with the rest of the community

The EU-Citizen.Science code is available on GitHub¹ under European Union Public License 1.2 (EUPL). This is a copyleft free/open source software license created on the initiative of and approved by the European Commission. Information about the Permissions, Limitations and Conditions of this license as well as the license itself can be found in the LICENSE² file of the repository.

The Horizon Europe project European Citizen Science (ECS) started on August 1, 2022 under

¹ https://github.com/lbercivis/EU-CS_platform

² https://github.com/lbercivis/EU-CS_platform/blob/master/LICENSE

Grant Agreement No. 101058509. This project, in which 21 European institutions participate (including the Ibercivis Foundation and ECSA) has among its tasks the participatory selection of new services for the EU-Citizen.Science platform (T2.2), the co-design and development of new services for the EU-Citizen.Science platform (T2.3) and the coordinated development of national/regional CS platform (T2.4). This project will end by July 2026 and ensures the maintenance and improvement of the services - including the connection to the VERA platform - offered by the EU-Citizen.science platform for at least the duration of the project.

The platform follows CS standards on metadata to describe the datasets stored on it. Of all of them, we describe in detail below the metadata related to projects, as they are the relevant ones for the connection between EU-Citizen.Science and VERA platforms. EU-Citizen.Science follows the Data Standard for Public Participation in Scientific Research (Citizen Science), known as PPSR Core. This standard is created, improved and maintained by the *Data and Metadata Working Group*³ composed of experts and members of various CS associations, such as the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), the Citizen Science Association (CSA) or the Australian Citizen Science Association (ACSA).

The Project Metadata Model (PMM) is a metadata model defined inside the PPSR Core that describes projects. Other models included in the PPSR Core are the Dataset Metadata Model (DDM) and the Observation Metadata Model (ODM). For the sake of clarity, we are presenting the interconnection between these three models in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Relationship between PMM, ODM and DMM Models (Image from the PPSR Working group)

³ <https://citizenscience.org/get-involved/working-groups/data-and-metadata-working-group/>

Project metadata provides the organising framework and context for data collection and tasks associated with a project and allows projects to be discovered and accessed by locations, time periods, themes, suitability, etc. It also enables project owners to explain to the world what their project is aiming to achieve and to encourage people to participate in it. It includes metadata which describes the context and purpose of activities. Key items include:

- Title and description of the project
- Ownership and contact information
- Temporal range of the project
- Spatial range of the project
- Partners and collaborators
- Funding, sponsorship and program alignment of the project
- Public participation and engagement information
- Links to other associated sites and resources
- Graphical elements associated with the project

The PMM is composed of different attributes and vocabularies, grouped into:

- [Core attributes](#) are the main fields associated with a project.
- [Extension attributes](#) are the fields whose inclusion is not mandatory for all systems that are compliant with PPSR Core.
- [The Vocabulary for Project](#) defines enumerations for attributes. These are controlled lists of defined terms. These terms may be used either as provided in full or as a reduced subset relevant to the purpose for which they are being used.

III. Why make this connection? The EU-Citizen.Science ecosystem

The vision for the EU-Citizen.Science platform is to serve as a Knowledge Hub, in aid of the mainstreaming of CS, and build on the growing impact of citizens participating in research across the full range of scientific inquiry. EU-Citizen.Science accomplishes this by supporting the sharing of knowledge, know-how, and experience between anyone doing or wanting to do CS. From its inception, EU-Citizen.Science was designed as a platform interconnected with other CS platforms. This connection allows, among other things:

- To have a single platform on which to visualise the vast majority of CS projects being carried out in Europe, resources useful for CS, etc.
- Information for projects, resources, etc to be updated at a single point, propagating the information automatically among all interconnected platforms (e.g. updating only on a national platform and propagating to EU-Citizen.Science platform).
- Connect third party applications that download information from the platform to, for example, analyse and study the current situation of CS in Europe.

The EU-Citizen.Science project has defined four types of connection with other platforms, namely:

- **Type 1, Interest:** The other platform has shown a continued interest in EU-Citizen.Science and also shares objectives.
- **Type 2, Share information:** The other platform is able to push and pull datasets (projects, resources, etc.) to EU-Citizen.Science through its API.
- **Type 3, Integration:** There is not other (technical) platform available, so the EU-Citizen.Science is used to store information (e.g. a country has no CS national platform and uses EU-Citizen.Science as their national platform)
- **Type 4, Fork:** The other platform uses EU-Citizen.Science source code to build a new CS platform.

Right now, up to 9 different platforms (including VERA) have established some degree of connection with the EU-Citizen.Science platform. Table 1 in the following page (p. 9) illustrates the growing use of the different types of connections EU-Citizen.Science has. Thus, the connection of VERA to EU-Citizen.Science not only enables the sharing of resources between the two platforms, but rather, enables it to be part of a growing ecosystem of CS information sharing.

Table 1. List of platforms connected (or in process to connect) to EU-Citizen.Science. This table is an updated version of Table 3: Inter-platform collaboration which appears on [Deliverable 2.4 EU-Citizen.Science Sustainability Plan](#)

Platform name	Country	Connection type	Status
VERA Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation H2020 COESO project	Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Portugal, Spain	2	Connection is completed by the release of this deliverable
Areas for co-operation through citizen science – ARCS Swedish national platform https://medborgarforskning.se/	Sweden	2	The Swedish platform was created using Wordpress CMS. A plug-in was created to store projects on EU-Citizen.Science and pull Swedish projects from EU-Citizen.Science. The last release of the Platform will provide the multilingual support needed by the ARCS platform.
Science ensemble and Particip-Arc French citizen science platforms	France	2	Both French platforms are working on the connection to the EU-Citizen.Science platform through the API to send French projects to EU-Citizen.Science. The French platforms need multilingual support to do so because one platform has projects in English and French and the other one only in French.
Citizen Science for the Amazon Network	Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, France, Peru, the United States	2,4	The Amazon CS platform is exploring both types of collaboration.
Spanish citizen science platform	Spain	4	The adoption of the code of EU-Citizen.Science is planned. The platform will be shared with Portugal
Ciência Viva	Portugal	4	The adoption of the code of EU-Citizen.Science is planned. The platform will be shared with Spain
CS Track H2020 project	Austria, Belgium, Finland, Germany, Greece, Israel, Spain	2	Both platforms have connected through the API and the CS Track project has pulled data on CS projects from EU-Citizen.Science to contribute to their work in building a CS evidence base.
Danish citizen science platform	Denmark	2	The Danish CS network has expressed interest in connecting via a plug-in with WordPress in the future.
Brazilian citizen science platform https://civis.ibict.br/	Brazil	4	Full use of EU-Citizen.Science source code in their CS platform. Developers from Brazil are participating in the development of EU-Citizen.Science code.

IV. Connection components, API description and its usage

As can be seen in the table above, the interconnection between VERA and EU-Citizen.Science is type 2, that is, it is done through its API. *An API is a way for two or more computer programs to communicate with each other. It is a type of software interface, offering a service to other pieces of software. A document or standard that describes how to build or use such a connection or interface is called an API specification. A computer system that meets this standard is said to implement or expose an API. The term API may refer either to the specification or to the implementation*⁴.

The EU-Citizen.Science platform was built using the Django framework. *Django is a high-level Python web framework that encourages rapid development and clean, pragmatic design. Built by experienced developers, it takes care of much of the hassle of web development.[...] It's free and open source*⁵.

On top of the EU-Citizen.Science models the API was built using the Django REST framework⁶. Django REST framework is a powerful and flexible toolkit for building Web APIs.

The API is accessible through the <https://eu-citizen.science/api/> endpoint. The EU-Citizen.Science code is also compatible with the Swagger⁷ library for Django⁸, which provides richer information on the API as well as information about models built with-in the EU-Citizen.Science platform. The swagger endpoint is available on <https://eu-citizen.science/swagger/>. In particular, there were created endpoint in order to:

- Manage authentication
- Create, edit, delete and pull organisations
- Create, edit, delete and pull projects
- Translate projects
- Create, edit, delete and pull resources
- Create, edit, delete and pull training resources

The figure in the following page (p.11) shows the Project model (the main model shared between EU-Citizen.Science and VERA platforms), as well as its relation to some other models of the EU-Citizen.Science platform.

⁴ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/API>

⁵ <https://www.djangoproject.com/>

⁶ <https://www.django-rest-framework.org/>

⁷ <https://swagger.io/>

⁸ <https://django-rest-swagger.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Figure 2. Project model and its relation with other models

As said previously, the API can be used throughout the <https://eu-citizen.science/api/> endpoint. For development purposes, another endpoint was created under the <http://dev.ibercivis.es:10000> URL. Both endpoints have the same behaviour. The main components for the connection between the EU-Citizen.Science and VERA platforms are the authentication and the project related ones.

During the execution of Task 3.6 “Interoperability development with EU-Citizen.Science platform” we used the Postman⁹ tool in order to share documentation¹⁰ and best practices on how to use the EU-Citizen.Science API. The documentation for authentication and project related tasks is shown below:

POST login

dev.ibercivis.es:10000/api/auth/token/login

This endpoint is used to authenticate and user. The output is the authentication token used for restricted calls

BODY urlencoded

email	frasan@bifi.es
password	12345678

Figure 2. Login endpoint usage

⁹ <https://www.postman.com/>

¹⁰ <https://documenter.getpostman.com/view/5316329/UVJckGTh>

POST Translate

```
dev.ibercivis.es:10000/api/projectTranslate/354
```

This call is used to translate a project. You need to know the projectID.

The fields that can be translated are only that you can see in this example

AUTHORIZATION API Key

HEADERS

Authorization Token 2d71c92d8314cf520358cbf99814b2754452eac0

BODY formdata

translatedDescription Description updated

translatedAim Aim2222211111

translatedHowToParticipate Howtotototo

translatedEquipment Equipment

inLanguage fr

Example Request
Translate

```

POST /api/projectTranslate/354 HTTP/1.1
Host: dev.ibercivis.es:10000
Authorization: Token 2d71c92d8314cf520358cbf99814b2754452eac0
Content-Length: 581
Content-Type: multipart/form-data; boundary=----WebKitFormBoundary7l
----WebKitFormBoundary7MA4YWxkTrZu0gW
Content-Disposition: form-data; name="translatedDescription"
Description updated

```

[View More](#)

Figure 3. Translate endpoint usage

POST projectPatch

dev.ibercivis.es:10000/api/projectTranslate/1

This call is used to edit a project

AUTHORIZATION API Key

HEADERS

Authorization Token 611f1ed2a6ef39ff31c01af4fc3516ccdd37ee32

PARAMS

Authorization Token 611f1ed2a6ef39ff31c01af4fc3516ccdd37ee32

BODY formdata

translatedDescription Description

translatedAim Aim

translatedHowToParticipate Howto

translatedEquipment Equipment

inLanguage es

Example Request
projectPatch

```

POST /api/projectTranslate/1 HTTP/1.1
Host: dev.ibercivis.es:10000
Authorization: Token 611f1ed2a6ef39ff31c01af4fc3516ccdd37ee32
Content-Length: 557
Content-Type: multipart/form-data; boundary=----WebKitFormBoundary7I

----WebKitFormBoundary7MA4YwXkTrZu0gW
Content-Disposition: form-data; name="+translatedDescription"
Description

```

[View More](#)

Figure 4: Edit project endpoint usage

POST projectCreate

dev.ibercivis.es:10000/api/projectCreate/

This call is used to create a project

AUTHORIZATION API Key

HEADERS

Authorization Token 611f1ed2a6ef39ff31c01af4fc3516ccdd37ee32

PARAMS

Authorization Token 611f1ed2a6ef39ff31c01af4fc3516ccdd37ee32

BODY formdata

name	Name
aim	Aim
description	Description
keywords	Key1, key2
status	1
start_date	2010-01-01
end_date	2020-02-01
topic	1
topic	2
hasTag	1
hasTag	2
participationTask	1
participationTask	2
difficultyLevel	2

difficultyLevel	2
howToParticipate	Howto
equipment	equipment
geographicextent	2
projectlocality	asd
author	info publicContactPoint
author_email	info@ibercivis.es publicContactPointEmail
mainOrganisation	1
organisation	2
organisation	3
image1	
image2	
image3	

```

Example Request projectCreate
POST /api/projectCreate/ HTTP/1.1
Host: dev.ibercivis.es:10000
Authorization: Token 611f1ed2a6ef39ff31c01af4fc3516ccdd37ee32
Content-Length: 2712
Content-Type: multipart/form-data; boundary=----WebKitFormBoundary7
----WebKitFormBoundary7MA4YwXkTrZu0gW
Content-Disposition: form-data; name="name"
Name
  
```

Figure 5: Create project endpoint usage

GET Get project

```
dev.ibercivis.es:10000/api/project/1
```

This call is used to get all the information from a project

Figure 6: Create project endpoint usage

Table 2 illustrates all the fields included in the Project model, which can be sent from VERA through the API. Some attribute names differ from the model names created in the source code.

Table 2. Project attributes used in EU-Citizen.Science

Attribute (PPSR)	Equivalent attribute In EU-Citizen.Science	Description	Type	Obligation
projectId	id	Globally unique identifier (GUID) for the project System generated.	integer	N/A
Mandatory fields				
projectName	name	Short name or title of the project.	text	Mandatory
projectUrl	url	An HTTP URL to an external web site for the project.	uri	Mandatory
projectDescription	description	Abstract or long description of the project.	text	Mandatory

projectAim	aim	The primary aim, goal or objective of the project.	text	Mandatory
	description_citizen_science_aspects	Description of the citizen science aspects of the project and the link to citizen science drawing on the ECSA Ten Principles on CS and Characteristics of CS. Only for moderation purposes.	text	Mandatory
projectStatus	status	The activity status of the project.	vocabulary: <i>Not yet started</i> <i>Active</i> <i>Periodically active</i> <i>On hold</i> <i>Completed</i> <i>Abandoned</i>	Mandatory
keyword	keywords	Keywords (comma separated) which are indexed and aid in searching for and finding projects.	text	Mandatory
Useful information to classify the project				
projectStartDate	start_date	The actual date that the project began. Uses the ISO 8601:2004 (E) dateTime standard.	Date Time	Optional
projectEndDate	end_date	The actual date that the project ended. Uses the ISO 8601:2004 (E) dateTime standard	Date Time	Optional
projectScienceType	topic	category of science represented by the project. Where the project fits into the landscape of science.	vocabulary (not following PPSR Core suggested vocabulary)	Optional
hasTag	hasTag	A set of categorical tags to assist with searching and filtering.	vocabulary: <i>Fees applicable</i> <i>Suitable for children</i> <i>Teaching materials available</i> <i>Do-it-yourself</i> <i>Participate from home</i>	Optional
Participation information				
scientificProcessesInvolved	participationTask	Parts of the process of science that participants exercise	Vocabulary: <i>Annotation</i>	Optional

			<i>Audio or video recording</i> <i>Classification or tagging</i> <i>DIY</i> <i>hacking/making</i> <i>Data analysis</i> <i>Data entry</i> <i>Download software for distributed computing</i> <i>Finding entities</i> <i>Geolocation</i> <i>Identification</i> <i>Learning</i> <i>Measurement</i> <i>Observation</i> <i>Photography</i> <i>Problem solving</i> <i>Sample analysis</i> <i>Site selection and/or description</i> <i>Specimen/sample collection</i> <i>Transcription</i>	
difficultyLevel	difficultyLevel	Assessed class of project difficulty for untrained participants to undertake. This attribute is used to assist with searching and filtering.	Vocabulary: <i>Easy</i> <i>Medium</i> <i>Hard</i>	Optional
projectHowToParticipate	howToParticipate	Free text description of how people can get involved in the project. Textual instructions for joining the project.	text	Optional
projectEquipment	equipment	Required or suggested equipment to be used in the project.	text	Optional
Project Location				
	geographicextent	Spatial scale of the project. Not in PPSR core	Vocabulary: <i>Global</i> <i>Macro-regional</i> <i>National</i> <i>Sub-national</i> <i>Regional</i> <i>City</i> <i>Neighbourhood</i>	Optional
projectLocality	projectlocality	Other textual location specification	text	Optional

projectGeographicLocation	projectGeographicLocation	User-defined geospatial representation point location or geographic extent of the project. Point locations are typically represented as map pins and extents as polygons. Uses OGC GeoAPI (09-083r3) standard. This is a class object.	Class	Optional
Contact and host details				
contactPoint	author	Name the contact person or contact point of the project.	text (a class on PPSR Core)	Optional
projectResponsiblePartyContactEmail	author_email	A contact email address of the party (eg. Organisation) that is responsible for implementing/conducting the project.	text	Optional
	mainOrganisation	Organisation leading the project. Not part of the PPSR Core	class	Optional
	organisation	Other Organisations involved on the project. Not part of the PPSR Core	class	Optional
Funding information				
projectFunding	fundingBody	Type(s) and source(s) of funding contributions to the project. This is a class object.	Text (a class on PPSR Core)	Optional
projectFundingSource	fundingProgram	Name of the programme that funds or funded the project. Not part of the PPSR Core	text	Optional
Project profile images				
projectMedia1 projectMedia2 projectMedia3	Image1 Image2 image3	Images used to graphically enhance or represent the project.	Class	Optional

V. VERA built-in connection to EU-Citizen.Science

The integration between VERA and EU-Citizen.Science must consider both technical and operational aspects.

The former are in a sense pretty straightforward: via EU-Citizen.Science APIs we can send the details about a VERA project. From an implementation viewpoint we will base the communication on asynchronous queues. When a project is set for publication, a message with its ID is inserted in the "create" queue, implemented by exploiting the features of the Laravel PHP framework, the technology that is used to develop VERA's business logic and its back-end.

A Laravel service, listening to this queue, retrieves all the details about the project and invokes the EU-Citizen.Science **projectCreate** API: the structure of its payload is described in the previous chapter. In order to be fully compliant with this API, some modifications in the VERA's project data model are needed.

First of all, the "description_citizen_science_aspects" field that allows project managers to explain in detail the citizen science aspects of the project is needed. This will facilitate in fact EU-Citizen.Science's administrators to evaluate if the project is suitable or not for the inclusion in their platform.

Those who want to submit a project to be published on EU-Citizen.Science directly, have in fact to fill in a field "description_citizen_science_aspects" which is mandatory (cfr Table 2 above) but whose content is meant for moderation purposes only and won't be published in the project data when approved.

Other meaningful fields that are currently missing from VERA are the name and the email of the contact person for the project (author and author_email). This kind of information might help in the evaluation phase, for example if EU-Citizen.Science administrators need to contact the VERA project administrators for clarifications.

Of course only a "public" project in VERA can be suitable for being published in EU-Citizen.Science. On the other hand it is important to make VERA's project managers fully aware of this possibility, by explicitly asking their consent.

In this sense, it has been decided to extend the VERA project settings with a dedicated EU-Citizen.Science section, that includes the missing fields cited above and that must be filled out if a VERA project manager accepts to publish her/his project. We can either request specific approval from the project manager to initiate the synchronisation with EU-Citizen.Science or consider an "implicit" acceptance if (s)he fills out these fields. In this section an explanation of the whole process can be presented, stating also very clearly that:

- there will be no guarantee that the project is sent or published on EU-Citizen.Science: as explained below, VERA administrators might decide to cancel the synchronisation or EU-Citizen.Science supervisors refuse the publication on their portal
- It will not be possible to automatically delete a project from EU-Citizen.Science (there

isn't a DELETE API).

Technically speaking the API mechanism will only synchronise data about a project and not create user credentials (e.g. those of the VERA project manager). Every VERA project in fact will be associated with a single "default VERA user", defined in EU-Citizen.Science.

While we mentioned above only the creation of a project, another specific service, still to be implemented by using an asynchronous queue, must be developed to manage the editing of a project (PATCH /project/{id} API) when specific events happen (e.g. when the project is closed or archived).

As indicated above, the technical aspects of the integration are not particularly complex, besides that some modifications and the development of the services to interact with EU-Citizen.Science APIs are needed on the VERA side. On the other hand the actual operational workflow to decide if and when a project can be submitted to EU-Citizen.Science will be more fully defined as VERA moves into public beta testing (especially from the perspective of the sustainability of VERA after the end of COESO).

For the moment we have decided to opt for a *double acceptance*, one in VERA and another, as explained in the following chapter, in EU-Citizen.Science.

As far as VERA is concerned, the implementation strategy that will be followed is:

- We extend the Back-End of VERA to add one flag in the Project form: "Publish to external sites". This flag must appear only in the Laravel back-end, so it must not appear in the Project settings of VERA, used by project managers. Only a VERA administrator can see and manage this flag
- The flag must be disabled if:
 - the project is "Private",
 - the fields of the EU-Citizen.Science section (see above) are not filled out
- With the necessary conditions met, the administrator can set the flag to TRUE.

When this happens, the ID of the project is put in the dedicated Laravel queue to start the synchronisation, as described above.

VI. Formal acceptance of VERA's projects within the EU-Citizen.Science platform

The project and (training) resource profiles on the EU-Citizen.Science platform are submitted by the CS community or the EU-Citizen.Science and ECS project consortia. Before publishing, they undergo a moderation process where the quality criteria framework developed within the EU-Citizen.Science project is applied. Partners in the EU-Citizen.Science project have developed these criteria and assessment framework as part of *WP3 Content - Framework, Quality Assurance and Curation*.

The ambitious goal for EU-Citizen.Science was to become the place to share useful resources about planning, running, evaluating and participating in CS initiatives or simply learning about CS, including tools and guidelines, best practices and training modules. It is important for the community of practitioners to have a way of ensuring that the projects profiled on the platform are indeed CS initiatives. This is why EU-Citizen.Science has a moderation process for all submissions.

When creating a profile for a project to share on the platform, a range of descriptive information about it (both in the platform itself and the API), and all of the mandatory data fields need to be completed before submitting the profile. Upon submission, it will be sent for moderation. Until it has been reviewed against EU-Citizen.Science's criteria, it will be marked as 'not yet moderated', and will not be automatically visible in search results. Once the project profile has successfully been through the moderation process, it will be marked as 'moderated', and will be fully available in search results. Thus, projects must meet certain criteria, which can be summarised as:

- The project is about CS or relevant to CS (required)
- All mandatory metadata is provided (required)
- The project engages with the ECSA 10 Principles of CS (suggested)

To enable the project provider to give more relevant information, the field *Description of CS aspects* was created. This field does not appear publicly in the project profile shown to the rest of the users of the platform, but is used by the moderator to make a more accurate decision on whether or not to accept a project.

Projects coming from the VERA platform will pass the same filter as all other EU-Citizen.Science projects in order to be published. However, not all projects generated within VERA will be sent to the EU-Citizen.Science platform since within VERA, due to its nature, there will be projects at a very early stage. Only projects that are under implementation or in their last design phase prior to implementation will be sent from VERA to EU-Citizen.Science.

VII. Conclusions

The current deliverable covers all work done to implement the connection between EU-Citizen.Science and VERA platforms. This work has been done in Task 3.6 Interoperability development with EU-Citizen.Science platform. This document provides an overview of the current initial integration flow which will evolve in the future.

Although most of the work has been technical, the present document also includes an approval flow - described in section VI - under which VERA projects will be accepted within EU-Citizen.Science. This approval flow is based on the current initial integration and it is open to further evolutions.

The connection has followed the state of the art of metadata standards for the definition of citizen science projects. In this way, it will be possible to easily establish the connection of VERA with other citizen science platforms - such as scistarter.org. This connection can be direct or via EU-Citizen.Science platform.

This connection opens up new possibilities for enhancing the EU-Citizen.Science platform - such as integrating the DELETE endpoint in API. As the ECS project will continue improving the EU-Citizen.Science platform, all suggestions that have arisen and continue to arise during the development of the VERA platform will be taken into account during the improvement of EU-Citizen.Science within ECS.